

**Photochemical Reaction between Bromine and
(1) Cinnamic Acid, (2) Stilbene.**

Part II.

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In a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1926, 2, 261) the results of investigations on reaction between bromine and (1) cinnamic acid, and (2) stilbene in carbon tetrachloride solution were published. White light was used for illuminating the system. It was found that the velocity of reaction can be roughly expressed by a unimolecular equation with respect to bromine. A reference to Tables VIII to XIII in that paper will at once indicate that the unimolecular velocity constant increases a little during the first few minutes, attains a maximum and then diminishes as the concentration of the reacting constituents diminishes, the magnitude of the diminution being 10 to 12 per cent. It was considered necessary to decide definitely whether these variations were due to experimental error or whether they are determined by the mechanism of the reaction.

It was also shown in that paper that the rate of reaction depended upon the concentration of the acceptor molecules of stilbene or cinnamic acid, the inverse of the rate of reaction plotted against the inverse of the concentration of acceptor molecules giving a straight line. Berthoud (*Faraday Soc. Disc.* held in Oct., 1925, published in March, 1926) has given the following mechanism of the reaction,

and obtains the following equation for the velocity of reaction.

$$\text{For strong absorption } \frac{dx}{dt} = kI^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{Br}_2]$$

$$\text{For weak absorption } \frac{dx}{dt} = kI^{\frac{1}{2}} [\text{Br}_2]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

"The rate of reaction is obviously independent of the conc. of the acceptor as long as this concentration is not very weak." This statement is in contradiction to the result we have obtained before. The reaction was therefore subjected to a thorough re-investigation specially in view of the fact that Berthoud has not published his experimental data by means of which the accuracy of our results could be checked.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The methods of investigation were the same as before except that in the measurement of the incident radiation a Moll thermopile and a Moll galvanometer were used. By the aid of coloured filter solutions recommended by Plotnikow, parallel beams of blue and green light were isolated and their photochemical action was studied separately. The following filters were used :—

- (1) For blue light between $\lambda=494\mu\mu$ to $458\mu\mu$
 - (a) methyl green 0.2 gm. per litre (1 cm. thick).
 - (b) copper sulphate 150 gms. per litre (2 cm. thick).
- (2) For green light between $\lambda=540\mu\mu$ to $505\mu\mu$
 - (a) potassium chromate 200 gms. per litre (2 cm. thick).
 - (b) copper chloride 600 gms. per litre (2 cm. thick).

The reaction vessel used in the experimental had the following dimensions :—

Height	Breadth	Thickness
2.0 cm.	1.5 cm.	1.5 cm.

It was necessary for purposes of exact interpretation of experimental data that the molecular extinction coefficient of bromine for various wave-lengths in the solvents used should be known. This was measured by means of the König-Martens spectrophotometer. The values of molecular extinction coefficient are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Solvent	Molecular extinction coefficient of bromine.					
	592 $\mu\mu$	579 $\mu\mu$	546 $\mu\mu$	533 $\mu\mu$	488.5 $\mu\mu$	436 $\mu\mu$
CS ₂	4.4	8.54	24.51	31.5	86.2	198.4
CCl ₄	2.68	5.5	15.6	19.7	50.1	97.6

It will be noticed that throughout the visible spectrum the extinction coefficient of bromine in carbon disulphide is 1.5 to 2 times that in carbon tetrachloride solution. In the molecule of carbon tetrachloride all the valencies of the atoms constituting the molecule are more or less completely saturated and hence the field of force round the molecule is very weak. In carbon disulphide however, the field of force round the molecule is much larger due to the unsatisfied latent valencies of the sulphur atoms. The larger extinction coefficient of bromine in carbon disulphide may be due to a complex produced by the association of carbon disulphide molecule with bromine.

The Influence of Concentration of Acceptor Molecules on the Velocity of Photobromination.

For accurate determination of this factor the following simplifying conditions were adhered to.

(a) Blue light was used; the extinction coefficient of bromine for this light being very large, the whole of the incident radiation is practically absorbed even by dilute solution of bromine, there being no appreciable variation of absorbed radiation for small changes in concentration of bromine during the course of the reaction.

(b) The initial concentration of the acceptor molecules, as will be evident from Table II, was always in excess of the concentration of the photoactive bromine molecules.

(c) A definite but small period of induction has been noticed before; to avoid this initial disturbance two concentrations of bromine x_1 and x_2 were measured 6 and 20 minutes after starting the reaction. It will be at once evident from Table II that the concentration of cinnamic acid for each experiment during this

interval of 14 minutes did not change perceptibly as the change in the conc. of bromine during this time never exceeded $\cdot 002$ M. If Berthoud's equation,

$$\frac{2.3}{t} \log \frac{x_1}{x_2} = k \text{ were correct,}$$

the values of k would have remained constant throughout. The values of k as obtained experimentally are recorded in column 3 of Table II. They show a regular diminution as the initial concentration of cinnamic acid diminishes.

TABLE II_xSolvent- CS_2 .Temp. 30°C

Blue light.

Initial concentration of bromine in each experiment = 0.0071 M

Conc. of cinnamic acid.	Osmotic pressure in mm.	k	k^1
$\cdot 06$ M	1121.6	$\cdot 0455$	21.98
$\cdot 08$ M	560.9	$\cdot 0425$	23.53
$\cdot 0225$ M	420.6	$\cdot 0391$	25.57
$\cdot 015$ M	280.6	$\cdot 0356$	26.1
$\cdot 01$ M	187.0	$\cdot 029$	34.48

The inverse of osmotic pressure plotted against the inverse of k gives a straight line. Extending the equation of Turner (see our previous paper, *loc. cit.*, p. 261) to this case we obtained for

$$Aa^2\tau = \frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}} = \frac{18.9}{30.8} = 0.00628.$$

from which $\tau = 2.24 \times 10^{-10}$ sec., where τ is the life period of the excited photosensitive constituent.

Table III gives the experimentally determined values of τ for photobromination under different conditions of experiment.

TABLE III.

Solvent.	Acceptor.	$Ia^{\circ}\tau$
CS ₂	Cinnamic acid	0.0022
CS ₂	Stilbene	0.0185
CCl ₄	Cinnamic acid	0.0021
CCl ₄	Stilbene	0.0063

It is accordingly necessary to modify the equation and also the reaction mechanism by Berthoud in a way which will make possible a systematic explanation of our experimental results. It should be pointed out at the outset that in our previous paper we obtained the equation (*loc.cit.*, p. 267),

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = C(a-x) \frac{\tau}{T+\tau}$$

where $(a-x)$ is the concentration of molecular bromine, τ is the life-period of the excited photosensitive constituent and T the interval between collision of the excited component and the acceptor molecule. The method of deduction of this equation as given before appears now to have been unsound in that the extinction coefficient of bromine was considered to be small. This statement is true for white light as a whole, but the velocity of reaction has been now found to be mostly determined by the blue and green radiations in the wave train, and the extinction coefficient of bromine for these radiations is very large (see Table I).

Our experimental results which are recorded in this paper in Table IV to XIV can be best explained by the following mechanism of reaction:

A chain mechanism leading to the regeneration of bromine atom is necessary in order to account for our experimental observation

that under different experimental conditions the number of dibromide molecules formed varies between 50 and 150 (Table XIX) for each quantum of light absorbed. The fourth process determines the speed of the reaction: (3) and (4) render back the bromine atoms consumed by (2). Thus (1) and (5) are in continual equilibrium and the concentration of free bromine atom at any instant is given by the relation,

$$k_1 I [1 - e^{-\epsilon [\text{Br}_2]^l}] = k_2 [\text{Br}]^2$$

$$\text{or } [\text{Br}_2] = \sqrt{\frac{k_1}{k_2} I} [1 - e^{-\epsilon [\text{Br}_2]^l}]$$

for green and blue light ϵ is very large;

$$\therefore [\text{Br}] = \sqrt{\frac{k_1}{k_2} I}$$

Assuming that all molecular species involved in this reaction except Br_2 is pretty stable, but that Br_2 has a very short life-period τ , it follows that the concentration of Br_2 at any instant is practically determined by reactions (2) and (3) and has the value

$$[\text{Br}_2] = \frac{k_3}{k_4} [\text{Br}] [\text{Br}_2]$$

This is only true if the life-period of Br is not too small to allow of the application of the law of mass action in its ordinary form to (2). The rate of formation of the dibromide and hence the rate of disappearance of bromine is (from 4) proportional to the concentration of Br_2 at any instant multiplied by the factor $\tau/T + \tau$ where T is the interval between the collision of a Br_2 molecule and an acceptor molecule of stilbene or cinnamic acid.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dc}{dt} &= k_4 [\text{Br}_2] \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \\ &= \frac{k_3}{k_4} \sqrt{\frac{k_1}{k_2} I} [\text{Br}_2] \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \\ &= k \sqrt{I} (a + x) \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \end{aligned}$$

But $\tau = Aa^2 p$ where p is the osmotic pressure in mm. of the acceptor molecules. Again $p = k\theta (c - x)$ where $(c - x)$ is the concentration of acceptor in gm. mols. per litre, θ the absolute temperature and k is a constant which can be easily evaluated (Van't Hoff's Law).

$$\text{Hence } \frac{dx}{dt} = k \sqrt{I} (a-x) \cdot \frac{\tau A \alpha^2 k \theta (c-x)}{1 + \tau A \alpha^2 k \theta (c-x)}$$

$$\text{putting } \tau A \alpha^2 k \theta = B,$$

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k \sqrt{I} (a-x) \cdot \frac{B (c-x)}{1 + B(c-x)}$$

$$\text{or } dx \left[\frac{1 + B(c-x)}{B(a-x)(c-x)} \right] = k \sqrt{I} dt.$$

or on integration

$$\frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x} + \frac{1}{t B(c-a)} \log \frac{a(c-x)}{c(a-x)} = k \sqrt{I} = k_1.$$

In Table IV-XVI the values of k_1 given in column 3 are calculated from the above equation. The values of k_2 given in column 4 are obtained from the simple unimolecular equation.

It will be seen that the velocity of reaction at the initial stage shows a progressive increase for a period varying between 5 to 15 minutes. This is due to the fact that during this stage the concentration of Br as determined by the equation (1) and (5) is on the increase. To avoid this initial disturbance the velocity constants given in the tables are calculated from the second reading as the initial value.

TABLE IV.

Green light; Intensity = .15 Hefner ;

Solvent CS_2 ; Acceptor—cinnamic acid; Initial conc.—.0238 M
Temperature $30^\circ C$; $B=120$.

Time in min.	(a-x)—conc. Br, mols. per litre.	k_1	k_2
0	.0197
8	.01756
16	.01455	.0324	.0285
25	.012	.0314	.0284
38.5	.009	.0318	.022
53.5	.00675	.0308	.0205

TABLE V.
Intensity=1 Hefner.

Time in min.	$(a-x)$ - conc. Br ₂ mols. per litre.	k_1	k_2
0	·02628
5	·02085
9·5	·0149	·105	-0742
15	·0099	·110	·0741
20·3	·0073	·108	·0690
31	·0045	·099	·0588

TABLE VI.
Solvent CCl₄; Intensity=1 Hefner; $B=40$.

0	·01962
17·5	·01532
39·5	·01117	·0307	·0143
84	·00675	·0291	·0128

TABLE VII.
Intensity=0·15 Hefner.
Solvent CS₂; Acceptor—stilbene; Initial conc.—0·0238 M
Temp. 30°C; $B=360$.

0	·0197
16	·0186
38·7	·0158	·0121	·0107
54·5	·0123	·0121	·0105
75	·01035	·0114	·0098

TABLE VIII.

Intensity=1 Hefner.

Time in min.	($a-x$)-conc. Br ₂ mols. per litre.	k_1	k_2
0	·02628
16	·0156
27	·01087	·0473	·037
36	·00775	·0470	·035

TABLE IX.

Blue light; Intensity=1 Hefner.

Solvent CS₂; Acceptor—Cinnamic acid; Initial Conc.—0·0258 M.
Temp. 30°C; B=120.

0	·0197
11	·01575
20	·0111	·058	·059
27	·00855	·059	·038
33·5	·00675	·060	·0377
41·5	·00525	·059	·036

TABLE X.

Blue light; Intensity=·066 Hefner

Solvent CS₂; Acceptor—cinnamic acid; Initial conc.—0·0238M
Temp. 30°C; B=120.

0	·02628
8·5	·01362
11	·0108	·203	·108
14·1	·00782	·206	·099

TABLE XI.

Solvent CCl_4 ; Intensity= $\cdot 1$ Hefner; Temp. 30°C ; $B=40$.

Time in min.	($a-x$)—conc. of Br_2 mols. per litre.	k_1	k_2
0	$\cdot 01962$
12	$\cdot 0198$
35	$\cdot 0145$	$\cdot 0228$	$\cdot 01$
55	$\cdot 01215$	$\cdot 0221$	$\cdot 00955$
108	$\cdot 0075$	$\cdot 0239$	$\cdot 00928$

TABLE XII.

Acceptor—stilbene. Intensity= $0\cdot 66$ Hefner; $B=120$.

0	$\cdot 02617$
20	$\cdot 02197$
31	$\cdot 0188$	$\cdot 0244$	$\cdot 0166$
41	$\cdot 0156$	$\cdot 0247$	$\cdot 0163$
52	$\cdot 0132$	$\cdot 0254$	$\cdot 0159$

TABLE XIII.

Solvent CS_2 ; $B=360$.

0	$\cdot 02628$
10	$\cdot 0201$
16.1	$\cdot 0135$	$\cdot 078$	$\cdot 065$
28	$\cdot 0092$	$\cdot 077$	$\cdot 061$

TABLE XIV.

Time in min.	(a-x)—conc. of Br ₂ mols. per litre.	k ₁	k ₂
0	·0197
5·8	·01522
9	·0128	·074	·067
14	·00905	·074	·0635

TABLE XV.

Blue light.

Solvent	Intensity	Acceptor	k ₁	k ₂
CCl ₄	·66	Cinnamic acid	·075	·026-·024
CCl ₄	·66	Stilbene	·0246	·017-·016

A comparison of the columns 3 and 4 in the tables given above will show that while k_2 undergoes regular diminution in value with increase in time, the values of k_1 are more or less concordant. This uniformity in the value of k_1 is evidence in favour of the mechanism of reaction we have proposed. It should be pointed out that while in green light the constancy of the values of k_1 is always much better than that of k_2 , in blue light however, in some of our experiments, k_1 has a tendency to increase slightly as the reaction progresses. There is one drawback however in that other experimental conditions remaining the same, the ratio of the velocity constants k_1 is not proportional to the sq. root of the ratio of the incident intensities. In Table XVI, the ratio of velocity constants are compared with intensity ratios.

TABLE XVI.

Quality of light.	Solvent.	Acceptor.	$\frac{k_2}{k_1}$	$\frac{k_2}{k_1}$	$\frac{I}{I'}$	$\sqrt{\frac{I}{I'}}$
Blue	CCl ₄	Cinnamic acid.	$\frac{·025}{·0096} = 2·6$	$\frac{·075}{·0227} = 3·3$	6·6	2·57
Blue	CS ₂	..	$\frac{·1}{·0877} = 2·65$	$\frac{·21}{·059} = 3·5$	6·6	2·57
Green	$\frac{·069}{·022} = 3·14$	$\frac{·11}{·032} = 3·44$
Green	..	Stilbene	$\frac{·036}{·0105} = 3·4$	$\frac{·047}{·012} = 3·9$

It will be noticed that for blue light the ratio of the simple unimolecular constants k_1 is approximately equal to the sq. root of the incident intensities ; for green light this is not the case. The ratio of the velocity constants is much larger than $\sqrt{I'I'}$ but always much less than $I'I'$. It is possible that simultaneously with the formation of bromine atoms, excited molecules of bromine may be produced by the absorption of light and these may cause a chain mechanism of the following type.

It is obvious that for strong absorption of light according to this mechanism of reaction,

$$kI = k_1' = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x} + \frac{1}{tB} \frac{1}{(c-a)} \log \frac{a(c-x)}{c(a-x)}$$

k_1 will be proportional to the incident intensity. If these two processes happen simultaneously the ratio of velocity constants will lie between the simple ratio of the intensities and the sq. root of their ratio.

It may be argued that the diminution of the value of k_1 is not due to diminution in the concentration of the acceptor molecules but is due to the fact that the whole of the incident blue or green radiation is not absorbed by the bromine solution and for that reason the amount of light absorbed diminishes as the concentration of bromine decreases during the progress of the reaction. It is possible to calculate approximately the correction that should be applied to the unimolecular constant k_1 if only this factor is to be taken into consideration. The original unimolecular equation has the form,

$$-\frac{dx}{dt} = kx \sqrt{I(1 - e^{-\epsilon x l})}$$

or

$$x \sqrt{1 - e^{-\epsilon x l}} = -k \sqrt{I} dt$$

$$\text{or } \frac{dx}{x} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} e^{-\epsilon x l} + \frac{1}{8} \cdot \frac{3}{2} e^{-2 \epsilon x l} + \dots \right] = -k \sqrt{I} dt$$

$$\text{or } \int_a^x \frac{dx}{x} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} e^{-\epsilon x l} + \frac{1}{8} \cdot \frac{3}{2} e^{-2 \epsilon x l} + \dots \right] = -k \sqrt{I} t$$

$$\text{or } \int_x^a \frac{dx}{x} + \frac{1}{2} \int_x^a \frac{e^{-\epsilon \cdot x \cdot l}}{x} dx + \frac{1}{4} \int_x^a \frac{e^{-2\epsilon \cdot x \cdot l}}{x} dx + \dots = k\sqrt{I}t$$

$$\text{or } \log \frac{a}{a-x} + \frac{1}{2} \left[li e^{-\epsilon \cdot l(a-x)} - li e^{-\epsilon \cdot l \cdot a} \right] \\ + \frac{1}{4} \left[li e^{-2\epsilon \cdot l(a-x)} - li e^{-2\epsilon \cdot l \cdot a} \right] + \dots = k\sqrt{I}t$$

$$\text{or } \log \frac{a}{a-x} + S = k\sqrt{I}t$$

The values of $li e^{-\epsilon \cdot l \cdot a}$ can be obtained from De Morgan's "Calculus" and the values of S can be evaluated. This has been actually done and it was found that for blue light of $\lambda=488 \mu\mu$, the correction term S is always negligible. In the case of green light ($\lambda=538 \mu\mu$) in CCl_4 solution the value of S varies from '0012 to '0018 as bromine concentration varies from '02 to '01 M. In CS_2 solution the variation in the value of S is still smaller. It is clear therefore that this correction term is not at all sufficient to account for the regular diminution in the value of unimolecular constant k , with the progress of reaction.

The temperature coefficient of the reaction between bromine and cinnamic acid has been determined in different regions of the spectrum. The experimental results are given in Table XVII.

TABLE XVII.

Temperature coefficient between 30° and 40°.

Solvent	Blue 488 $\mu\mu$	Green 538 $\mu\mu$	White-light
CCl_4	2.45	2.65	2.74
CS_2	2.7	2.8	2.85

It is evident from the result that the temperature coefficient increases with the wave-length of light. The dark reaction has no doubt a large temperature coefficient but the dark reaction is very small in comparison with the light reaction.

The relation between photochemical efficiency and wave-length of light is given in Table XVIII. It will be seen that in CCl_4 solution the number of molecules of cinnamic acid transformed into dibromide per quantum of light absorbed varies from 22 to 48, and in CS_2 solution the number is 3 to 4 times greater.

TABLE XVIII.

Temp.	Solvent	Acceptor	No. of mols. transformed per quantum of Blue (488 $\mu\mu$)	per quantum of Green (533 $\mu\mu$)
30°C	CCl ₄	Cinnamic acid	43	22
"	"	Stilbene	34	16
"	CS ₂	Cinnamic acid	156	101
"	CS ₂	Stilbene	99	52

Summary.

1. The photobromination of cinnamic acid and stilbene has been studied in CCl₄ and CS₂ solutions in blue and green light.

2. It has been found that there is a regular diminution in the value of the unimolecular velocity constant with increase in time. This has been explained by assuming the following mechanism for the reactions:—

3. The temperature coefficient of the light reaction has been found to increase with the wave-length of incident radiation.

4. The average life-period of the intermediate activated molecule in the photobromination of cinnamic acid and stilbene has been determined and found to be of the order of 10⁻⁹ secs.

5. Molecular extinction coefficient of bromine in carbon disulphide for different wave-lengths has been measured.

6. In blue light the unimolecular velocity constant varies as the sq. root of the intensity of incident radiation but the increase is greater in green light.

7. The rate of reaction depends upon the concentration of the acceptor molecules.

8. The photochemical efficiency of the wave-lengths 488 $\mu\mu$ and 533 $\mu\mu$ for the bromination of cinnamic acid and stilbene has been measured. In the case of cinnamic acid in carbon tetrachloride the number of molecules transformed into dibromide per quantum of 488 $\mu\mu$ is 43, of 533 $\mu\mu$ 22. In carbon disulphide the number of molecules transformed per quantum is much greater.

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